

Image Representation of Executables Code

```
def exe_to_image(exe_path, output_path):  
    with open(exe_path, "rb") as f:  
        byte_data = f.read()  
  
    if len(byte_data) == 0:  
        raise ValueError("Executable file is empty")  
  
    byte_array = np.frombuffer(byte_data, dtype=np.uint8)  
  
    total_bytes = len(byte_array)  
    width = int(np.ceil(np.sqrt(total_bytes)))  
    height = int(np.ceil(total_bytes / width))  
  
    padded_bytes = np.pad(  
        byte_array,  
        (0, width * height - total_bytes),  
        mode="constant"  
    )  
    img_array = padded_bytes.reshape((height, width))  
  
    img = Image.fromarray(img_array, mode="L")  
  
    img = img.resize((224, 224), Image.BILINEAR)  
  
    img_normalized = np.array(img).astype(np.float32) / 255.0  
  
    Image.fromarray(  
        (img_normalized * 255).astype(np.uint8),  
        mode="L"  
    ).save(output_path)  
  
    print("Executable converted to grayscale image successfully")
```

Model 1: CNN+ Temporal Convolutional Network Code

1. Data Loading and Preprocessing

```
def load_dataset(base_path):
    image_paths, labels1, labels2, labels3 = [], [], [], []

    for family in sorted(os.listdir(base_path)):
        family_path = os.path.join(base_path, family)

        if not os.path.isdir(family_path):
            continue

        if family == "Benign":
            for img in os.listdir(family_path):
                image_paths.append(os.path.join(family_path, img))
                labels1.append("Benign")
                labels2.append("None")
                labels3.append("None")
        else:
            for subfamily in sorted(os.listdir(family_path)):
                sub_path = os.path.join(family_path, subfamily)
                if not os.path.isdir(sub_path):
                    continue
                for img in os.listdir(sub_path):
                    image_paths.append(os.path.join(sub_path, img))
                    labels1.append("Malware")
                    labels2.append(family)
                    labels3.append(subfamily)

    X = []
    for path in tqdm(image_paths, desc=f"Loading grayscale images"):
        try:
            img = Image.open(path).convert('L').resize((224, 224))
            img = np.array(img) / 255.0
            X.append(img)
        except:
            continue
    X = np.array(X).reshape(-1, 224, 224, 1)

    le1 = LabelEncoder()
    y1 = to_categorical(le1.fit_transform(labels1))

    le2 = LabelEncoder()
```

```

y2 = to_categorical(le2.fit_transform(labels2))

le3 = LabelEncoder()
y3 = to_categorical(le3.fit_transform(labels3))

return X, y1, y2, y3, le1, le2, le3
X_train, y1_train, y2_train, y3_train, le1, le2, le3 = load_dataset(train_path)
X_val, y1_val, y2_val, y3_val, _, _, _ = load_dataset(val_path)
X_test, y1_test, y2_test, y3_test, _, _, _ = load_dataset(test_path)

```

2. CNN+ Temporal Convolutional Network Model Architecture

```

def build_cnn_tcn_model(input_shape=(224, 224, 1)):

    input_layer = Input(shape=input_shape)

    x = Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(input_layer)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)
    x = Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(x)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)
    x = Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(x)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)
    x = Reshape((28*28, 128))(x)
    x = TCN(nb_filters=64, kernel_size=3, dilations=[1, 2, 4, 8], return_sequences=False)(x)
    x = Dropout(0.5)(x)
    shared_dense = Dense(128, activation='relu')(x)
    output1 = Dense(2, activation='softmax', name='malware_output')(shared_dense)
    output2 = Dense(6, activation='softmax', name='family_output')(shared_dense)
    output3 = Dense(34, activation='softmax', name='subfamily_output')(shared_dense)
    model = Model(inputs=input_layer, outputs=[output1, output2, output3])
    return model

```

3. Model Compilation

```
model = build_cnn_tcn_model()

model.compile(
    optimizer=Adam(learning_rate=0.0001),
    loss={
        'malware_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'family_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'subfamily_output': 'categorical_crossentropy'
    },
    metrics={
        'malware_output': 'accuracy',
        'family_output': 'accuracy',
        'subfamily_output': 'accuracy'
    }
)
```

4. Model Training Procedure

```
history = model.fit(
    X_train,
    {
        'malware_output': y1_train,
        'family_output': y2_train,
        'subfamily_output': y3_train
    },
    validation_data=(
        X_val,
        {
            'malware_output': y1_val,
            'family_output': y2_val,
            'subfamily_output': y3_val
        }
    ),
    epochs=50,
    batch_size=32
)
```

5. Test Set Evaluation

```
test_results = model.evaluate(X_test, {'malware_output': y1_test,  
  
    'family_output': y2_test,  
  
    'subfamily_output': y3_test})  
  
print("\n Malware vs Benign Accuracy:", round(test_results[4]*100, 2), "%")  
  
print(" Malware Family Accuracy: ", round(test_results[5]*100, 2), "%")  
  
print(" Subfamily Accuracy:    ", round(test_results[6]*100, 2), "%")
```

Model 2: CNN + Capsule Network Code

1. Data Loading and Preprocessing

```
def load_dataset(base_path):
    image_paths, labels1, labels2, labels3 = [], [], [], []
    for family in sorted(os.listdir(base_path)):
        family_path = os.path.join(base_path, family)
        if not os.path.isdir(family_path):
            continue
        if family == "Benign":
            for img in os.listdir(family_path):
                image_paths.append(os.path.join(family_path, img))
                labels1.append("Benign")
                labels2.append("None")
                labels3.append("None")
        else:
            for subfamily in sorted(os.listdir(family_path)):
                sub_path = os.path.join(family_path, subfamily)
                if not os.path.isdir(sub_path):
                    continue
                for img in os.listdir(sub_path):
                    image_paths.append(os.path.join(sub_path, img))
                    labels1.append("Malware")
                    labels2.append(family)
                    labels3.append(subfamily)

X = []
for path in tqdm(image_paths, desc=f"Loading grayscale images"):
    try:
        img = Image.open(path).convert('L').resize((224, 224))
        img = np.array(img) / 255.0
        X.append(img)
    except:
        continue
X = np.array(X).reshape(-1, 224, 224, 1)

le1 = LabelEncoder()

y1 = to_categorical(le1.fit_transform(labels1))

le2 = LabelEncoder()
```

```

y2 = to_categorical(le2.fit_transform(labels2))

le3 = LabelEncoder()

y3 = to_categorical(le3.fit_transform(labels3))

return X, y1, y2, y3, le1, le2, le3

X_train, y1_train, y2_train, y3_train, le1, le2, le3 = load_dataset(train_path)

X_val, y1_val, y2_val, y3_val, _, _, _ = load_dataset(val_path)

X_test, y1_test, y2_test, y3_test, _, _, _ = load_dataset(test_path)

```

2. Capsule Layer Implementation

```

class CapsuleLayer(tf.keras.layers.Layer):

    def __init__(self, num_capsules, dim_capsule, routings=3, **kwargs):

        super(CapsuleLayer, self).__init__(**kwargs)

        self.num_capsules = num_capsules

        self.dim_capsule = dim_capsule

        self.routings = routings

    def build(self, input_shape):

        self.input_num_capsules = input_shape[1]

        self.input_dim_capsule = input_shape[2]

        self.W = self.add_weight(shape=[self.num_capsules, self.input_num_capsules,

                                         self.dim_capsule, self.input_dim_capsule],

                                initializer='glorot_uniform',

                                trainable=True)

    def call(self, inputs):

        inputs_expand = tf.expand_dims(inputs, 1)

        inputs_tile = tf.tile(inputs_expand, [1, self.num_capsules, 1, 1])

```

```

inputs_hat = tf.map_fn(lambda x: tf.matmul(self.W, x, transpose_b=True), elems=inputs_tile)

b = tf.zeros(shape=[tf.shape(inputs_hat)[0], self.num_capsules, self.input_num_capsules])

for i in range(self.routings):

    c = tf.nn.softmax(b, axis=1)

    outputs = tf.reduce_sum(c[..., None] * inputs_hat, axis=2)

    outputs = self.squash(outputs)

    if i < self.routings - 1:

        b += tf.reduce_sum(inputs_hat * outputs[:, :, None, :], axis=-1)

return outputs

def squash(self, s):

    s_norm = tf.norm(s, axis=-1, keepdims=True)

    return s_norm**2 / (1 + s_norm**2) * s / (s_norm + tf.keras.backend.epsilon())

```

3. CNN+Capsule Networks Model Architecture

```

def build_cnn_capsnet(input_shape=(224, 224, 1)):

    input_layer = Input(shape=input_shape)

    x = Conv2D(64, (5, 5), activation='relu', padding='same')(input_layer)
    x = Conv2D(128, (5, 5), activation='relu', padding='same', strides=(2, 2))(x)
    x = Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu', padding='same')(x)
    x = Flatten()(x)
    x = Dense(1152, activation='relu')(x)
    x = Reshape((24, 48))(x)

    capsule = CapsuleLayer(num_capsules=10, dim_capsule=16, routings=3)(x)
    capsule = Flatten()(capsule)
    capsule = Dense(128, activation='relu')(capsule)
    capsule = Dropout(0.5)(capsule)

```

```
output1 = Dense(2, activation='softmax', name='malware_output')(capsule)
output2 = Dense(6, activation='softmax', name='family_output')(capsule)
output3 = Dense(34, activation='softmax', name='subfamily_output')(capsule)

model = Model(inputs=input_layer, outputs=[output1, output2, output3])
return model
```

4. Model Compilation

```
model = build_cnn_capsnet()

model.compile(
    optimizer=Adam(learning_rate=0.0001),
    loss={
        'malware_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'family_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'subfamily_output': 'categorical_crossentropy'
    },
    metrics={
        'malware_output': 'accuracy',
        'family_output': 'accuracy',
        'subfamily_output': 'accuracy'
    }
)
```

5. Model Training Procedure

```
history = model.fit(
    X_train,
    {
        'malware_output': y1_train,
        'family_output': y2_train,
        'subfamily_output': y3_train
    },
```

```
validation_data=(
    X_val,
    {
        'malware_output': y1_val,
        'family_output': y2_val,
        'subfamily_output': y3_val
    }
),
epochs=50,
batch_size=32
)
```

6. Test Set Evaluation

```
test_results = model.evaluate(X_test, {'malware_output': y1_test,

                                     'family_output': y2_test,

                                     'subfamily_output': y3_test})

print("\n Malware vs Benign Accuracy:", round(test_results[4]*100, 2), "%")

print(" Malware Family Accuracy: ", round(test_results[5]*100, 2), "%")

print(" Subfamily Accuracy:      ", round(test_results[6]*100, 2), "%")
```

Model 3: CNN + BiLSTM Code

1. Data Loading and Preprocessing

```
def load_dataset(base_path):
    image_paths, labels1, labels2, labels3 = [], [], [], []
    for family in sorted(os.listdir(base_path)):
        family_path = os.path.join(base_path, family)
        if not os.path.isdir(family_path):
            continue
        if family == "Benign":
            for img in os.listdir(family_path):
                image_paths.append(os.path.join(family_path, img))
                labels1.append("Benign")
                labels2.append("None")
                labels3.append("None")
        else:
            for subfamily in sorted(os.listdir(family_path)):
                sub_path = os.path.join(family_path, subfamily)
                if not os.path.isdir(sub_path):
                    continue
                for img in os.listdir(sub_path):
                    image_paths.append(os.path.join(sub_path, img))
                    labels1.append("Malware")
                    labels2.append(family)
                    labels3.append(subfamily)

X = []
for path in tqdm(image_paths, desc=f"Loading grayscale images"):
    try:
        img = Image.open(path).convert('L').resize((224, 224))
        img = np.array(img) / 255.0
        X.append(img)
```

```

    except:
        continue
X = np.array(X).reshape(-1, 224, 224, 1)

le1 = LabelEncoder()

y1 = to_categorical(le1.fit_transform(labels1))

le2 = LabelEncoder()

y2 = to_categorical(le2.fit_transform(labels2))

le3 = LabelEncoder()

y3 = to_categorical(le3.fit_transform(labels3))

return X, y1, y2, y3, le1, le2, le3

X_train, y1_train, y2_train, y3_train, le1, le2, le3 = load_dataset(train_path)

X_val, y1_val, y2_val, y3_val, _, _, _ = load_dataset(val_path)

X_test, y1_test, y2_test, y3_test, _, _, _ = load_dataset(test_path)

```

2. CNN+ Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory Model Architecture

```

def build_cnn_bilstm_model(input_shape=(224, 224, 1)):
    input_layer = Input(shape=input_shape)

    x = Conv2D(32, (3, 3), padding='same', activation='relu')(input_layer)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)

    x = Conv2D(64, (3, 3), padding='same', activation='relu')(x)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)

    x = Conv2D(128, (3, 3), padding='same', activation='relu')(x)
    x = MaxPooling2D((2, 2))(x)

    x = Reshape((28*28, 128))(x)

    x = Bidirectional(LSTM(64, return_sequences=False))(x)
    x = Dropout(0.5)(x)

    shared_dense = Dense(128, activation='relu')(x)

    output1 = Dense(2, activation='softmax', name='malware_output')(shared_dense)

```

```
output2 = Dense(6, activation='softmax', name='family_output')(shared_dense)

output3 = Dense(34, activation='softmax', name='subfamily_output')(shared_dense)
model = Model(inputs=input_layer, outputs=[output1, output2, output3])
return model
```

3. Model Compilation

```
model = build_cnn_bilstm_model()

model.compile(
    optimizer=Adam(learning_rate=0.0001),
    loss={
        'malware_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'family_output': 'categorical_crossentropy',
        'subfamily_output': 'categorical_crossentropy'
    },
    metrics={
        'malware_output': 'accuracy',
        'family_output': 'accuracy',
        'subfamily_output': 'accuracy'
    }
)
```

4. Model Training Procedure

```
history = model.fit(
    X_train,
    {
        'malware_output': y1_train,
        'family_output': y2_train,
        'subfamily_output': y3_train
    },
    validation_data=(
        X_val,
        {
            'malware_output': y1_val,
```

```
        'family_output': y2_val,  
        'subfamily_output': y3_val  
    }  
),  
epochs=50,  
batch_size=32  
)
```

5. Test Set Evaluation

```
test_results = model.evaluate(X_test, {'malware_output': y1_test,  
                                     'family_output': y2_test,  
                                     'subfamily_output': y3_test})  
  
print("\n Malware vs Benign Accuracy:", round(test_results[4]*100, 2), "%")  
  
print(" Malware Family Accuracy: ", round(test_results[5]*100, 2), "%")  
  
print(" Subfamily Accuracy:    ", round(test_results[6]*100, 2), "%")
```

Required Libraries

Core system libraries

```
import os
import sys
import glob
import time
import random
import shutil
import warnings
```

Numerical and data processing

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
```

Image processing

```
from PIL import Image
import cv2
```

Progress monitoring

```
from tqdm import tqdm
```

Visualization

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

Machine learning utilities

```
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.metrics import (
    classification_report,
    confusion_matrix,
    accuracy_score,
    precision_score,
    recall_score,
```

```
    f1_score
)
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

Deep learning framework

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.layers import (
    Input, Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Dense, Flatten,
    Dropout, Reshape, GlobalAveragePooling1D,
    BatchNormalization, Activation,
    Bidirectional, LSTM
)
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import Adam
from tensorflow.keras.utils import to_categorical
from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import (
    EarlyStopping,
    ModelCheckpoint,
    ReduceLROnPlateau
)
from tensorflow.keras import backend as K
```

Temporal Convolutional Network

```
from tcn import TCN
```

Model saving and serialization

```
import h5py
import pickle
```

